

TRIGONOMETRIK FUNKSIYALAR BILAN BOG'LIQ MASALALARNI GEOMETRIK USULDA YECHISH

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Annotatsiya. Maqola trigonometrik funksiyalar bilan bog'liq masalalarni geometrik usullarda yechish haqida.

Trigonometrik funksiyalarga bog'liq masalalarni geometrik teoremlar, gipotezalar, eng asosiysi chizmalar orqali yechish usullari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: funksiya, trigonometrik funksiya, ayniyat, chizma, uchburchak.

Аннотация. Статья о решении задач, связанных с тригонометрическими функциями, геометрическими методами.

Приведены способы решения задач, связанных с тригонометрическими функциями, с помощью геометрических теорем, гипотез и, самое главное, чертежей.

Ключевые слова: функция, тригонометрическая функция, тождество, чертеж, треугольник.

Annotation. The article is about solving problems related to trigonometric functions using geometric methods.

It presents methods for solving problems involving trigonometric functions through geometric theorems, hypotheses, and, most importantly, drawings.

Keywords: function, trigonometric function, identity, drawing, triangle.

Biz trigonometriyadagi hisoblashlarni, ayrim trigonometrik formulalarning isbotini geometrik usullarda hal qilish haqida to'xtab o'tamiz. Ba'zi masalalarni geometrik va algebraik yechish usullarini keltiramiz.

1-misol. $tg15^{\circ}$ ni hisoblang.

$$1\text{-usul. } tg15^{\circ} = tg(60^{\circ} - 45^{\circ}) = \frac{tg60^{\circ} - tg45^{\circ}}{1 + tg60^{\circ}tg45^{\circ}} = \frac{\sqrt{3} - 1}{\sqrt{3} + 1} = \frac{(\sqrt{3} - 1)^2}{2} = 2 - \sqrt{3}.$$

2-usul. ABC to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakni qaraymiz. ($AB = BC$) $\angle ABC = 30^{\circ}$. Bu uchburchakda AD va BE balandliklar tushiramiz.

$$\angle CAD = 15^{\circ}, \quad tg15^{\circ} = \frac{CD}{AD}.$$

Agar $AD = 1$ bo'lsa $AB = 2$ va $BD = \sqrt{3}$.

Demak, $CD = 2 - \sqrt{3}$

(1-chizma)

1-chizmadan foydalanib $\sin 15^\circ$, $\cos 15^\circ$, $\operatorname{ctg} 15^\circ$ larni oson hisoblash mumkin.

2-misol. $\operatorname{tg} 22^\circ 30'$ ni hisoblang.

1-usul. $|\operatorname{tg} \alpha| = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos 2\alpha}{1 + \cos 2\alpha}}$ formulani qo'llasak $\operatorname{tg} 22^\circ 30' = \sqrt{2} - 1$ ga teng.

2-usul. ABC burchagi 45° bo'lgan ABC ($AB=BC$) teng yonli uchburchakni qaraymiz.
 $\angle BCA = 67^\circ 30'$ bo'lgani uchun $\angle CAD = 22^\circ 30'$

$$\operatorname{tg} 22^\circ 30' = \frac{CD}{AD}.$$

$AD=1$ bo'lsin, u holda

$CD=BC-BD=AB-AD=\sqrt{2AD^2} - AD = \sqrt{2} - 1$ ga teng bo'ladi. Xuddi 1-masaladagi kabi $\sin 22^\circ 30'$, $\cos 22^\circ 30'$, $\operatorname{ctg} 22^\circ 30'$ larni hisoblash mumkin.

3-masala. $\cos 32^\circ - \cos 72^\circ = \frac{1}{2}$ ayniyatni isbotlang.

Isboti: Bu ayniyatni algebraik usulda isbotlari trigonometriyadagi bir qator formulalarini qo'llashni taqozo etadi. Bular quydagilar:

$$\cos \alpha - \cos \beta = -2 \sin \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2} \sin \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2}$$

$$\sin(-\alpha) = -\sin \alpha$$

$$\sin \alpha = \cos(90^\circ - \alpha)$$

$$\sin 2\alpha = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$$

Biz bu ayniyatni teng yonli uchburchakdan foydalanib isbotlaymiz. ABC ($AB=BC$) uchburchak va D ($D \in BC$ va $AD=BD=AC$) nuqtani qaraymiz. Uchlari A, B, C, D nuqtalarda bo'lgan burchak kattaliklarini aniqlaymiz.

Agar $\angle ABC = x$ bo'lsa, $\angle BAD = x$, $\angle ADC = 2x$, $\angle ACD = 2x$, $\angle DAC = 2x$, $\angle ADB = 3x$.

Bu kattaliklar teng yonli uchburchakni burchaklari xossasi va uchburchakning tashqi burchagi xossasidan hosil bo'ldi. ABD, ACD va ABC uchburchakning tashqi burchaklari yig'indisi $5x$ ga teng. (2-chizma).

(2-chizma)

$$5x = 180^{\circ}, \quad x = 36^{\circ}.$$

Demak, $\angle ABC = 36^{\circ}$ va $\angle ADC = 72^{\circ}$.

$D \in BC$ bo'lgani uchun $BC = BD + DC$.

Agar $BD = 1$ bo'lsa, $AB = 2 \cos 36^{\circ}$ va $CD = 2 \cos 72^{\circ}$. $AB = BC$ bo'lgani uchun

$$2 \cos 36^{\circ} = 1 + 2 \cos 72^{\circ}.$$

Demak, $\cos 36^{\circ} - \cos 72^{\circ} = \frac{1}{2}$. Javob: $\frac{1}{2}$

4-misol. $\frac{1}{\sin\left(25\frac{5}{7}\right)^{\circ}} = \frac{1}{\sin\left(51\frac{3}{7}\right)^{\circ}} + \frac{1}{\sin\left(77\frac{1}{7}\right)^{\circ}}$ ayniyatni isbotlang.

Isbot. 1) $\triangle ABD, \triangle ADC$ va $\triangle ABC$ teng yonli uchburchak bo'lganligi uchun

$$7x = 180^{\circ}$$

$$x = \left(25\frac{5}{7}\right)^{\circ}$$

2) $BC = BD + DC$.

Agar $\triangle ABD, \triangle ADC$ va $\triangle ABC$ uchburchaklarda A uchidan tushirilgan umumiy balandlik 1 ga teng bo'lsa ($H \in BC, AH \perp BC, AH = 1$) u holda $\triangle ABH$ dan

$$(AH \perp BH) \quad BC = AB = \frac{AH}{\sin \angle ABH} = \frac{1}{\sin\left(25\frac{5}{7}\right)^{\circ}}$$

$$\triangle ADH \text{ dan } (AH \perp DH) \quad BD = AD = \frac{AH}{\sin \angle ADH} = \frac{1}{\sin\left(51\frac{3}{7}\right)^{\circ}}.$$

$$\triangle ACH \text{ dan } (AH \perp CH) \quad DC = AC = \frac{AH}{\sin \angle ACH} = \frac{1}{\sin\left(77\frac{1}{7}\right)^{\circ}}.$$

Demak, $\frac{1}{\sin\left(25\frac{5}{7}\right)^{\circ}} = \frac{1}{\sin\left(51\frac{3}{7}\right)^{\circ}} + \frac{1}{\sin\left(77\frac{1}{7}\right)^{\circ}}$. Isbotlandi.

5-misol. $\sin 18^{\circ}$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish.

1-usul. $\sin 36^{\circ} = \cos 54^{\circ}$

$$\sin 36^{\circ} = \cos(18^{\circ} + 36^{\circ})$$

$$2 \sin 18^{\circ} \cos 18^{\circ} = \cos 18^{\circ} \cos 36^{\circ} - \sin 18^{\circ} \sin 36^{\circ} \text{ yoki}$$

$$2 \sin 18^{\circ} \cos 18^{\circ} = \cos 18^{\circ} (1 - 2 \sin^2 18^{\circ}) - 2 \sin^2 18^{\circ} \cos 18^{\circ}$$

$$0 < \cos 18^{\circ} < 1 \text{ bo'lgani uchun}$$

$$2 \sin 18^{\circ} = 1 - 4 \sin^2 18^{\circ}$$

$$\text{Agar } \sin 18^{\circ} = x \text{ bo'lsa, } 4x^2 + 2x - 1 = 0$$

$$0 < x < \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{Bundan } \sin 18^{\circ} = \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{4}.$$

2-usul. 3-chizmadagi ABC va CAD uchburchaklar o'xshash. Ularning har ikkalasi asosidagi burchaklari ($\angle ACB = \angle ACD$) teng bo'lgan teng yonli uchburchaklardir. Demak,

$$\frac{AC}{AB} = \frac{CD}{AC}. \quad AC^2 = AB \cdot CD.$$

(3-chizma)

Agar $AC = a$ va $AB = b$ ($a < b$, $\angle ABC = 36^{\circ}$ va $\angle ACB = 72^{\circ}$) bo'lsa, $CD = b - a$ va $a^2 = b^2 - ab$.

Bundan $\frac{a}{b} = \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{2}$. Bu sonlar oltin kesim yoki Fidiya sonlari deyiladi. (Fidiya-Arximedning otasi).

$$\sin 18^{\circ} = \cos 72^{\circ}, \quad \cos 72^{\circ} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} CD}{AC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{AC}{AB} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{a}{b}.$$

$$\text{Demak, } \sin 18^{\circ} = \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{4}. \quad \text{Javob: } \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{4}.$$

Ko'rsatma: Bu masaladan foydalanib $\cos 36^{\circ}$, $\sin 36^{\circ}$, $\cos 18^{\circ}$ va ularning qiymatlarini oson topishimiz mumkin.

$$\cos 36^{\circ} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} AB}{AD} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{AB}{AD} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{b}{a} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5} - 1} = \frac{\sqrt{5} + 1}{4}.$$

Endi ba'zi bir trigonometrik ayniyatlarni isbotlashning geometrik usullariga to'xtab o'tamiz.

6-misol. $\sin^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha = 1$ (asosiy trigonometrik ayniyat) ni isbotlang.

Isbot: To‘g‘ri burchagi C bo‘lgan ABC to‘g‘ri burchakli uchburchakni qaraymiz.

(4-chizma). Gipotenuza $AB = 1$ bo‘lsin, u holda $BC = \sin \alpha$ va $AC = \cos \alpha$ Pifagor teoremasiga ko‘ra $\sin^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha = 1$.

(4-chizma)

7-misol. $1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha = \frac{1}{\cos^2 \alpha}$ ekanligini isbotlang.

Isbot. 4-chizmada ABC uchburchakning AC kateti 1 ga teng bo‘lsa, u holda $BC = \operatorname{tg} \alpha$, $AB = \frac{1}{\cos \alpha}$. Demak, Pifagor teoremasiga ko‘ra $1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha = \frac{1}{\cos^2 \alpha}$.

8-misol. $\sin 2\alpha = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$ ekanligini isbotlang.

Isbot: ABC teng yonli ($AB = BC = 1$) uchburchakni qaraymiz. ABC burchagi 2α ga teng bo‘lsin (5-chizma). AD va BE uchburchakning balandliklari bo‘lsin.

(5-chizma)

Chizmadan $AD = \sin 2\alpha$, $AE = EC = \sin \alpha$, $BE = \cos \alpha$.

ABE va CAD uchburchaklar o‘xshash.

$$\frac{AB}{AC} = \frac{BE}{AD}; \quad \frac{1}{2 \sin \alpha} = \frac{\cos \alpha}{\sin 2\alpha}.$$

Demak, $\sin 2\alpha = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Г.З.Генкин “Геометрические решения негеометрических задач” Москва. “Просвещение”. 2007.
2. A.S. Yunusov, S.I.Afonina va boshqalar “Qiziqarli matematika va olimpiada masalalari” Akademik litsey, kasb-hunar kollejlari uchun o‘quv qo‘llanma. Toshkent “O‘qituvchi”, 2007